

A Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach for Navigation and Control of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles in Complex Environments

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Abstract—The comprehension of the underwater environment is recently being accelerated by technological advances in sensors, robotics and Artificial Intelligence (AI). At the forefront of this evolution, lies the Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV), a sophisticated ocean exploration tool that is capable of performing underwater mapping, leveraging data obtained by onboard sensors. AUVs can navigate autonomously in unknown environments without any human interaction, while their level of autonomy is tightly linked to their path planning strategy. In this study, we perform a comparative analysis of a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method utilising two neural network models, a Linear Model (LM) that consists only of linear layers, and a Convolutional Model (CM) that consists of convolution layers for feature extraction that are merged with linear layers. Our evaluation focuses on assessing the performance of the proposed models for generating optimal paths in 3D underwater environments based on path length and obstacle avoidance. Through comprehensive simulations, we showcase the efficiency of our solution and present a comprehensive framework tailored for solving path planning problems in 3D complex underwater settings.

Index Terms—AUV, Actor-critic algorithm, AUV navigation, dynamic path planning, reinforcement learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The exploration of the ocean basin has always attracted research interest. In recent years, Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) have emerged as a groundbreaking fusion of robotics and marine technology, offering unparalleled versatility in underwater exploration, research, and monitoring, particularly in deep, remote, or hazardous marine areas where human access is almost impossible (1). AUVs are unmanned, and self-propelled while they can operate independently across a large geographical area for a long period (2). In recent years, they have gained an important economic place by being utilized in commercial, research, marine geosciences, and military applications (3).

Given the limited resources of underwater missions, autonomy is one of the most paramount assets of the AUVs capabilities. One of the core components of their autonomy lies in path planning, which defines the AUV's movement and decision-making processes, ranging from basic obstacle avoidance to complex mission execution (4). The term path planning refers to determining the most efficient route that allows the vehicle to navigate with obstacle avoidance and with respect to certain mission objectives, such as path length,

time of execution, obstacle avoidance, or energy consumption (5).

Recently, Reinforcement Learning (RL) methods (6) have emerged for offering significant potential to complex challenges of underwater navigation, due to their robust adaptation capabilities in response to various disturbances (7; 8). These methods exhibit great advantages, as they can interact with the environment, through policy formulation without extensive knowledge of AUV's dynamics or prior information of its surroundings (9). However, current research primarily focuses on simplified AUV models or studies that are constrained by unrealistic assumptions such as overlooking obstacles or considering a simplified 2D navigation environment.

This work proposes a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method based on the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm to address the AUVs path planning problem in a 3D navigation space. We evaluate the performance of two different architectures, a linear and a convolutional. The Linear Model (LM) consists of linear layers, with advantages that lie in its simplicity and interpretability. On the other side, the Convolutional Model (CM) consists of convolution layers which is preferred for high dimensional data.

The contributions of this work can be summarized in the following:

- A PPO-based method for AUV navigation in 3D environments, which is validated using two different and popular in recent literature neural network models
- A novel method for obtaining information about the navigation environment using a vision sensor, which allows robust trajectory generation without any prior knowledge of the search space, considering path length, obstacle avoidance, and overall operational success, as performance criteria.
- A full-scale system simulation for underwater exploration in a realistic underwater environment and can obtain optimal paths for AUVs.
- An evaluation of the proposed implementation in a simulated environment with challenging navigation scenarios, which allows moving one step closer towards an actual implementation on a real AUV.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section

It provides a review of existing literature on path planning methods for AUVs. In Section III, we introduce the preliminary knowledge of our work, including environmental modeling, dynamic and kinematic equations of the AUV, the PPO-based path planner framework, and proposed neural network models. Section IV presents the simulation results of the proposed PPO methodology. Finally, Section V concludes with insights into future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Several diverse path-planning methods have been recently explored in the literature, tailored to the specific operational requirements of AUV applications (2). Global path planning techniques generate optimal paths where the environment is predefined or can be mapped in advance, and thus are considered powerful tools for generating optimal paths in underwater scenarios, due to their low complexity and easy implementation (10). For example, the A* algorithm is popular for AUV navigation, providing low complexity solutions and good real-time performance (11). Different versions of the A* algorithm that vary on the heuristic function have been proposed in the literature for solving the path planning problems in strong ocean currents (12; 13). In addition, evolutionary computation algorithms, such as the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) (12), or the genetic algorithm (GA) (5) are efficient path planners for high-dimensional search spaces, while numerous improvements of the PSO algorithm have been recently proposed to increase robustness and enhance the global searching capability (14).

Local path planning methods are particularly well-suited for navigating in unknown or dynamic environments since they are based on real-time decision-making by obtaining their input from sensors. The Rapidly-exploring Random Trees (RRT) or the Artificial Potential Trees (15) have gained popularity due to their ability to explore high-dimensional configuration spaces efficiently (3; 11). DRL algorithms have also garnered significant attention for their ability to directly map underwater environments to continuous action spaces, allowing for reliable and real-time path planning (16). RL techniques, such as the Twin-Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (TD3) algorithm, have addressed specific challenges in local two-dimensional (2-D) path planning for AUVs (17). These methods outperform the conventional ones regarding path planning efficiency, generalization, and energy consumption by integrating mean function modifications with experience replay buffers. The PPO algorithm employs the concept of proximal policy optimization to achieve favorable outcomes in real-time control tasks such as maneuvering and obstacle avoidance across various categories of intelligent and autonomous vehicles (9; 18).

All the previously mentioned studies utilize value-based RL algorithms, which aim to estimate the value of different actions or states to inform decision-making. These algorithms seek to maximize the expected cumulative reward by selecting actions leading to higher-value outcomes. In contrast,

policy-based RL algorithms directly adjust policy parameters without involving maximization computations.

Motivated by these considerations, this study presents a PPO-based path-planning method for AUV navigation in a 3D simulated environment. Control inputs are obtained via a vision sensor using online measurements, enabling intelligent decision-making and obstacle avoidance for efficient path optimization. The proposed method undergoes validation across two distinct neural network architectures, evaluating criteria, such as path length and overall operational success. Additionally, a reward function related to safe collision avoidance action through an event-triggered mechanism is employed.

III. METHODOLOGY

This paper integrates DRL using the PPO algorithm and evaluates two distinct neural network architectures for AUVs. PPO is a policy gradient method designed to enhance training stability through a clipped surrogate objective. Its primary goal is to update the policy while limiting the magnitude of changes, ensuring more stable and reliable learning. PPO strikes a balance between exploration and exploitation by employing advantage estimation to assess how much better or worse a particular action is compared to the expected outcome.

The AUV is equipped with a vision sensor that enables it to detect both obstacles and the navigation target without needing prior knowledge of their positions. The simulator provides the distance to the target, while the target's position remains fixed. This information is accessed through the CoppeliaSim API, allowing us to calculate the distance between the AUV and the target after each action, and to determine the appropriate reward as outlined in the previous section. Given that the AUV operates in a non-grid-based environment with a camera, pressure, and collision sensors, grid-based algorithms such as A* and PSO are unsuitable and ineffective for this setting. For this reason, we tested our method using DRL algorithms that support Box-type spaces. The Box observation space is necessary because the AUV processes images with three channels (RGB), which require continuous data for input to the neural network. Similarly, the Box action space allows continuous control of movement, speed, and direction, which is crucial for smooth and realistic navigation in 3D environments. The DRL algorithms that satisfy these requirements are Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG), TD3, Advantage Actor Critic (A2C), and PPO.

The results indicate that DDPG and TD3 struggled to consistently find the target, while both A2C and PPO were successful. However, A2C required more steps and often took unnecessary actions, indicating less efficient training. On the other hand, PPO demonstrated superior performance, finding the target more quickly and efficiently due to more effective training.

An illustration, Figure 1, shows the trajectory of the AUV using each algorithm, highlighting the differences in performance.

Fig. 1. Evaluation of the state-of-the-art DRL algorithms

Algorithm 1 outlines the proposed approach. Within the initialization method, the environment, model, policy, and AUV model are all defined. This step sets the stage for training the algorithm by establishing the context in which it will operate. The neural network model is then instantiated to learn from the observed environment and make appropriate decisions for the AUV. Subsequently, a policy is established to govern the decision-making process of the model based on environmental states, guiding its actions. Additionally, an AUV model is initialized to translate the selected actions from the policy into commands understandable by the AUV, as well as interpret the feedback from the force sensors. The main training loop involves iterating through multiple training episodes. Within each episode, the environment state is initialized, and actions are selected based on the policy. These actions are translated into commands by the AUV model, executed in the environment, and the resulting rewards and next states are observed and stored. The policy is then trained using the collected data, optimizing it through the PPO method. This iterative process continues until the policy learns an effective strategy for the given environment. The pseudocode provides a clear and structured representation of the algorithm’s workflow, facilitating its understanding and implementation in practical applications.

Building on this, we evaluate our model’s generalization performance across 50 different starting points by initially training it at a single starting point. Subsequently, we train it at three different starting points to avoid overfitting and evaluate which model demonstrates superior generalization capabilities.

A. Reinforcement Learning Essentials and Dataset Description

In this experiment, we utilized images from a simulated 3D environment as shown in Figure 2 to create our dataset. All data are obtained through the vision sensor. The algorithm’s input comprised three main components: the observation space, action space, and reward function. The **observation**

Algorithm 1 Our Method: Deep Reinforcement Learning with Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)

Define Environment, Model, Policy, and AUV Model
Environment, Model, Policy, Model_AUV \leftarrow initialization()
Train Model
for episode = 1 **to** max_episodes **do**
Initialize state s (an image from the environment)
while episode not finished **do**
Select action a using Policy $\pi(a|s)$ (will translate into forces in Newton)
Send action a to AUV Model to translate to AUV commands
Execute action a , observe reward r and next state s' (update the environment)
Store transition (s, a, r, s')
Update state $s \leftarrow s'$
end while
Optimize Policy using PPO
end for
return Trained Policy

space was represented by a matrix of continuous integer values, reflecting the diversity of images captured by the vision sensor. The **action space** encompassed movements described in terms of vehicle coordinates ($O'-x',y',z'$), denoted by position ($x, y, \text{ and } z$) and orientation described by yaw as shown in Figure 3. Finally, the **reward** (r) function determined the agent’s reward post-action execution, with rewards inversely correlated to the distance (d) from the target (red cube), as shown in Equation (1).

$$r = \frac{1}{d} \cdot 10 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. 3D Coppelia World

Fig. 3. Action Space

The force system we adhere to enables realistic underwater exploration. Along the z -axis, we consider buoyancy and the weight of the AUV, ensuring equilibrium with the Equation (2):

$$\Sigma \vec{F}_z = 0 \quad (2)$$

By equating the upward force (A) and the downward force (W), as depicted in the Figure 4 below, we have:

$$\Sigma \vec{F}_z = 0 \implies \vec{A} + \vec{W} = 0 \implies A - W = 0 \implies A = W \quad (3)$$

When forces are applied due to the action, the principle of

$$\Sigma \vec{F} = m * \vec{a} \quad (4)$$

is applied to all three axes, with corresponding force components for each axis.

Fig. 4. Forces in the Equilibrium State

B. Performance Metrics

Following an extensive study, the fundamental performance metrics employed in our research, are as follows:

- **Target Reachability:** Measures the frequency of successful AUV arrivals at the predetermined destination across various path instances.
- **Collisions:** Enumerates instances where the AUV encounters obstacles or ground collisions during its path.
- **Timeouts:** Identifies paths where the AUV fails to reach the target within a specified time threshold post-takeoff.
- **Out-of-Limits Episodes:** Identifies paths where the AUV fails to reach the target within a specified time threshold post-takeoff.
- **Path Length:** Computed solely for successfully traversed paths across all models, representing the total action count necessary to navigate the AUV from its initial position to the final target.

C. Neural Network Models

We propose two distinct models, as shown in Figure 5, utilizing Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) as the activation function. ReLU's non-linearity allows neural networks to capture complex correlations within input data, which is essential for our problem domain. Our objective is to enable the agent to navigate to the target across various scenarios by learning from images and starting from three different locations.

ReLU's benefits also include reducing overfitting when training new models. By remaining inactive for negative input values, ReLU helps prevent the model from fitting noise in the data excessively (19). This is paramount to our task, as it ensures the agent's robustness in locating the target across diverse starting positions.

The first model, known as the **LM**, employs deep networks for both the Actor and Critic components. Each component

Fig. 5. Actor-Critic for both models

comprises three layers with 256, 128, and 64 units, respectively. ReLU activation is applied to each layer, enabling the network to capture non-linear relationships within the data.

In contrast, the second model, referred to as the **CM**, utilizes convolutional layers as feature extractors instead of the Flatten method. These convolutional layers with 64, 128, and 256 filters successively, aim to capture hidden spatial patterns present in the input data. ReLU activation follows each convolutional layer. The advantage of the CM over the LM lies in its architecture tailored for image inputs. This design allows the network to extract relevant features while preserving critical spatial structures essential for our problem domain.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The experimental study is simulated using the Coppelia Sim application. In this section, we compare the two different neural network models used in the PPO algorithm employed by the AUV for navigation in the environment and obstacle avoidance, based on the metrics defined in previous section. Each interaction between the AUV and the environment constitutes an episode, which in this research concludes when one of the four above criteria is met. A successful episode occurs when the AUV manages to reach the target. Essentially, the higher the metric of Target Reachability, the more successful episodes there are.

Moreover, these metrics apply to both sets of evaluations described below. We compare both models on two different sets of starting points. In the first set, only one starting point was used to train the different neural networks and evaluated on 50 different starting points. In contrast, for the second set, both models were trained on three different starting points and re-evaluated on 50 different starting points. This aims to assess how the models respond when trained with more information about the environment. Training from three

different starting points provides more varied and extensive image data from the vision sensor, allowing the models to perceive a larger portion of the environment compared to training from just one starting point.

Based on this, we compare the two neural network models that have been trained in three different starting points, not only on the above four criteria but also on the length of the path in each successful episode to determine which model performs better and reaches the target faster. In other words, one can more easily find the shortest path, something crucial for autonomous vehicles, including AUVs, because the fewer steps required, the better for their autonomy as they won't need to utilize system resources for extended periods. Consequently, this comparison sheds light on the models' adaptability and generalization capabilities under different training conditions.

A. Experiment Results for Training using 1-Starting Point

The performance results of each model are displayed in Figures 6 and 7. It is observed that the CM model demonstrates the best performance, successfully reaching the target in 36% of the paths it selects. However, it is noteworthy that this success rate is accompanied by a relatively high collision rate with environmental objects, occurring 58% of the time, and exceeding the environment limits 6% of the time. On the other hand, the LM model shows comparatively lower performance, with only 12% of the episodes resulting in reaching the destination. In the majority of instances involving the LM model, collisions with obstacles occurred instead.

Fig. 6. Linear Model

Fig. 7. Convolutional Model

B. Experiment Results for Training using 3-Starting Points

The performance results of each model are depicted in Figures 8 and 9. Interestingly, the LM model showcased superior performance compared to the CM model. Specifically, the LM model achieved a commendable success rate, reaching the target in 82% of its navigation paths, with only 18% of these paths resulting in collisions with environmental obstacles. Conversely, the CM model exhibited a slightly lower success rate, with 78% of its navigation paths leading to the target, albeit with a slightly higher collision rate of 22%.

An interesting observation is that neither of the models encountered timeouts nor exceeded the predefined limits during the evaluation process. This indicates that both models were capable of efficiently navigating through the environment without encountering significant hindrances such as excessive steps or boundary violations.

Fig. 8. Linear Model

Fig. 9. Convolutional Model

In addition, we compared the path lengths for the common successful episodes. The CM model achieved the target 39 out of 50 times, while the LM model succeeded 41 times. However, the common starting points that both models identified and reached the target were only 32. This is evident in Figures 10 and 11. Additionally, we observed that the CM exhibited shorter minimum path lengths compared to the LM, indicating its efficiency in finding optimal paths. Despite this, the CM showed higher variability in path lengths. Therefore, the CM was able to discover the shortest paths and demonstrate better performance.

Fig. 10. Linear Model

Fig. 11. Convolutional Model

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This study investigated the optimization challenge of path planning for AUVs navigating through 3D environments

through evaluation, comparing the efficacy and robustness of the PPO algorithm for AUV navigation in uncharted territories. Its primary goal was to develop and assess a navigation solution that places emphasis on optimizing path length while ensuring collision avoidance. We conducted a thorough evaluation, comparing the efficacy and robustness of the PPO algorithm for AUV navigation in uncharted territories. Our results revealed that, our method successfully reached the target, showcasing its superior navigational capabilities.

For future improvements, we propose exploring additional RL algorithms tailored to AUV navigation, with a focus on energy optimization and motion parameters to develop a more reliable and precise approach. Testing in real-world conditions would further illuminate performance and robustness, particularly when facing unforeseen challenges.

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